

Design, synthesis and synergistic antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal activity of nitrogen heterocycles[†]

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Abstract : A convenient, facile and efficiently catalyzed synthesis of nitrogen heterocycles using aldehydes, 1,3-dicarbonyl and 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole/urea/thiourea/2-amino benzothiazole in the presence of L-proline at 65–70 °C under solvent free conditions is being described. Results clearly demonstrated that the effect of these heterocycles have quinazolines, quinazolinones and 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole especially *para* and *ortho* hydroxyl substituted derivatives being more pronounced for antioxidant activity. Results suggested that derivative 1c, 1d, 2b, 3a, 3b and 4 exhibited good inhibitory effect against tested bacterial species and derivatives 1c, 1d and 2b showed the good spectrum for fungal activity.

Keywords : Antioxidant activity, antimicrobial activity, green synthesis, cytotoxicity, heterocycles.

1. Introduction

Multi-component reactions (MCRs) have attracted much attention of synthetic organic chemists because of the building of complex molecules and incorporating multiple functionalities^{1–8}. Simple procedure, high bond forming efficiency, time and energy saving and low expenditures are advantages of these reactions. Quinazolines and octahydroquinazolinone analogues are important heterocycles that are present in many naturally accruing alkaloids, have possesses interesting pharmacological activities such as antihypertensive⁹, analgesic and anti-inflammatory¹⁰, anticancer¹¹ and anti-HIV activities¹². Triazole scaffold also having interesting pharmacological properties^{13–17}. Several methods have been developed for the preparation of quinazolinone derivatives involving reaction of aldehydes with SOCl₂ and pyridine, then with 2-amino benzylamine in a refluxing solvent such as benzene or xylene with azeotropic water removal, refluxing in ethanol/acetic acid mixtures and by reaction in alkali media, but all have resorted to harsh condition and low yield, as well use of expensive and hazardous chemical materials with side reactions¹⁸.

Lipson *et al.*¹⁹ have synthesized 1,2,4-triazoloqui-

nazoline derivatives with poor yields. Shaabani *et al.* have synthesized 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole derivatives using ionic liquid at 100 °C with poor yields²⁰. The drawbacks of ionic liquids are that it cannot be removed by distillation and their limited solubility in water restricts their use. They have high cost and also acute toxicity for aquatic organism and human^{21,22}. Rao *et al.*²⁴ have also synthesized these types of derivatives which suffer many drawbacks such as hazardous solvent, long reaction time, harsh reaction conditions and low yield. Methods reported for the synthesis of octahydroquinolinone and octahydroquinoline derivatives have also suffer several drawbacks like long reaction time, hazardous microwave condition, lower yield with side by-products and used of heavy and hazardous metal catalyst^{25–32}. We have synthesized the biologically active heterocyclic derivatives using L-proline under solvent free conditions. The utility of L-proline as catalyst led to formation of high yield (79–96%). L-Proline has not been reported as catalyst so far, hence this paper also reports this new catalyst for these nitrogen heterocyclic derivatives. All the synthesized compounds possess good antioxidant and antimicrobial activity.

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2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and methods :

The ^1H NMR spectra were measured by BRUKER AVANCE II 400 NMR spectrometer with tetramethylsilane as an internal standard at 20–25 °C; data for ^1H NMR are reported as follow : chemical shift (ppm), integration, multiplicity (s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; q, quartet; m, multiplet and br, broad), coupling constant (Hz). IR spectra were recorded by SHIMADZU, IR spectrometer of sample dispersed in KBr pellet and are reported in terms of frequency of absorption (cm^{-1}). Elemental analysis was performed by a Carlo-Erba EA1110 CNNO-S analyzer. Electrospray ionization mass spectroscopy was performed using an ion trap mass spectrometer (Model 6310 agilent). E. Merck pre-coated TLC plates, RANKEM silica gel G for preparative thin-layer chromatography were used. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. 2-Amino benzothiazole was purchased from Sigma Aldrich and other chemical were purchased from commercial supplier and used without any purifications. Brain heart infusionTM, Mueller-Hinton agar, Subourad dextrose agar and Subourad dextrose broth were purchased from OXOID LTD., Basingstoke, Hampshire, England. 96 Microwell with lid was purchased from IWAKI Brand SCITECH DIV. Asahi Techno Glass, Japan. All the solvents and reagents used for the synthesis were of analytical grade. 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH*) was procured from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA). Spectrophotometric studies were done on a UV-Visible spectrophotometer (GBC Cintra 10, Australia).

2.2. Typical procedure :

A mixture of aldehydes (0.0025 mol), dicarbonyl (0.0025 mol) and urea/thiourea/2-amino benzothiazole/3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (0.0025 mol) were heated at 65–70 °C under solvent free conditions using L-proline (10 mol%) as catalyst. After completion of the reaction (judged by TLC analysis), the contents was cooled to room temperature and poured in cold water then solid mass as target product was obtained. Crude product was crystallized by ethanol.

Characterization data

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1a) :

Pale-yellow crystals, m.p. 178–180 °C (Lit.¹³ 173–

175 °C); R_f = 0.47 (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) : 3043 (C-H_{str}), 2968 (C-H_{str} in CH_2CH_3), 1670 (C=O_{str}), 1589 (C=N_{str}), 1462 (C=C_{str}), 744 (C-H_{def}); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ_{H} 1.29 (3H, t, J_{HH} 7.12 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.46 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.17 (2H, m, CH_2CH_3), 6.39 (1H, s, -CH), 7.07–7.43 (9H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 165.44, 162.59, 154.04, 141.26, 137.43, 128.26, 127.98, 126.79, 126.40, 123.68, 122.92, 122.22, 111.65, 102.56, 59.35, 56.82, 23.17, 13.99; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$: 350.44, Found : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ 351.2; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 68.48; H, 5.13; N, 7.98. Found : C, 68.78; H, 5.38; N, 7.89.

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxy phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1b) :

Pale-yellow powder, m.p. 192–194 °C, R_f = 0.53 (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) : 3360 (OH_{str}), 3059 (C-H_{str}), 2983 (C-H_{str} in CH_2CH_3), 1703 (C=O_{str}), 1597 (C=N_{str}), 1504 (C=C_{str}), 740 (C-H_{def}); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ_{H} 1.31 (3H, t, J_{HH} 7.12 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.47 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.8 (3H, s, Ar-OCH_3), 4.12–4.19 (2H, m, CH_2CH_3), 6.36 (1H, s, -CH), 6.78 (1H, d, J_{HH} 5.6 Hz, ArH), 6.89–6.92 (2H, m, ArH), 7.13–7.31 (4H, m, ArH), 9.80 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 165.60, 162.34, 153.51, 147.12, 146.42, 137.61, 132.52, 126.37, 123.61, 122.91, 122.21, 119.48, 115.18, 111.92, 110.88, 102.88, 59.28, 56.55, 55.43, 23.09, 14.08; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$: 396.49, Found : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ 397.2; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for C, 63.55; H, 5.04; N, 7.06. Found : C, 63.68; H, 5.16; N, 7.13.

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(4-dimethylamino phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1c) :

Pale-yellow powder, m.p. 175–178 °C, R_f = 0.57 (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) : 3059 (C-H_{str}), 2897 (C-H_{str} in CH_2CH_3), 1612 (C=O_{str}), 1581 (C=N_{str}), 1431 (C=C_{str}), 815–754 (C-H_{def}); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ_{H} 1.29 (3H, t, J_{HH} 7.12 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.86 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.06 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.15 (2H, m, CH_2CH_3), 6.71–7.5 (4H, m, ArH), 7.71–7.92 (4H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 166.39, 165.44, 153.95, 152.63, 151.46, 133.43, 132.18, 127.71, 125.91, 124.45, 121.73, 120.57, 117.66, 111.53, 111.29, 110.74, 23.13, 13.60; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$: 393.54, Found : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ 394.2; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 67.08; H, 5.84; N, 10.67. Found : C, 67.16; H, 5.98; N, 10.75.

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(4-nitro phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1d) :

Yellow powder, m.p. 170–172 °C, $R_f = 0.52$ (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3348 (C-H_{str}), 2933 (C-H_{str} in CH₂CH₃), 1625 (C=O_{str}), 1510 (NO_{2str}), 1267 (C=C_{str}), 962–812 (C-H_{def}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 1.31 (3H, s, CH₂CH₃), 2.46 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.12–4.21 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 6.34 (1H, s, -CH), 7.07–7.58 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 166.25, 163.56, 155.83, 147.95, 147.62, 137.44, 128.06, 126.88, 124.43, 124.01, 123.73, 122.47, 111.36, 102.01, 60.42, 57.03, 23.97, 14.40; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₇N₃O₄S : 395.46, Found : [M+H]⁺ 396.4; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 60.69; H, 4.29; N, 10.62. Found : C, 60.78; H, 4.35; N, 10.70.

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(2-hydroxy phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1e) :

Pale-yellow powder, m.p. 212–215 °C, $R_f = 0.53$ (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3456 (OH_{str}), 3028 (C-H_{str}), 2810 (C-H_{str} in CH₂CH₃), 1668 (C=O_{str}), 1575 (C=N_{str}), 1485 (C=C_{str}), 837–750 (C-H_{def}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) : δ_H 1.29 (3H, t, J_{HH} 4.76 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.1–4.19 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 6.33 (1H, s, -CH), 6.66–7.92 (8H, m, ArH), 8.9 (1H, s, OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 171.88, 165.92, 162.99, 157.23, 151.33, 137.57, 133.73, 132.41, 128.14, 126.08, 122.92, 117.66, 116.07, 115.70, 59.26, 56.23, 23.11, 14.04; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈N₂O₃S : 367.34, Found : [M]⁺ 367.2; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 65.49; H, 4.91; N, 7.64. Found : C, 65.44; H, 4.93; N, 7.66.

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(4-hydroxy phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1f) :

Pale-yellow powder, m.p. 210–212 °C, $R_f = 0.59$ (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3288 (OH_{str}), 3059 (C-H_{str}), 2897 (C-H_{str} in CH₂CH₃), 1612 (C=O_{str}), 1581 (C=N_{str}), 1431 and 1377 (C=C_{str}), 815–754 (C-H_{def}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 1.25 (3H, t, J_{HH} 4.76 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.04–4.12 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 6.30 (1H, s, -CH), 6.66 (2H, d, J_{HH} 8.40 Hz, ArH), 7.13–7.59 (4H, m, ArH), 7.59 (1H, d, J_{HH} 7.76 Hz, ArH), 9.26 (1H, s, OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 165.55, 162.27, 157.22, 153.46, 137.56, 131.95, 128.13, 126.34, 123.57, 122.94, 122.20, 115.02,

111.80, 102.96, 59.27, 56.37, 23.09, 14.03; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for : C₂₀H₁₈N₂O₃S : 367.34, Found : [M]⁺ 367.2; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 65.49; H, 4.91; N, 7.64. Found : C, 65.51; H, 4.95; N, 7.62.

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(4-methoxy phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1g) :

Pale-yellow powder, m.p. 130–132 °C, $R_f = 0.53$ (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 2941 (C-H_{str} in CH₂CH₃), 1627 (C=O_{str}), 1508 (C=N_{str}), 1280 (C=C_{str}), 962–813 (C-H_{def}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 1.28 (3H, t, J_{HH} 4.76 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.71 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 4.11–4.21 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 6.34 (1H, s, -CH), 6.78 (2H, d, J_{HH} 8.64 Hz, ArH), 7.21–7.58 (6H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 166.67, 163.27, 159.42, 154.51, 138.06, 133.81, 128.51, 126.57, 123.82, 122.14, 120.89, 119.04, 113.90, 103.24, 57.20, 55.18, 23.73, 14.40; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₀N₂O₂S : 380.47, Found : [M+H]⁺ 381.3; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 66.23; H, 5.25; N, 7.35. Found : C, 66.26; H, 5.27; N, 7.35.

Ethyl-2-methyl-4-(2,6-dichloro phenyl)-4H-pyrimido[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-3-carboxylate (1h) :

Pale-yellow powder, m.p. 150–152 °C, $R_f = 0.56$ (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 3012 (C-H_{str}), 2922 (C-H_{str} in CH₂CH₃), 1625 (C=O_{str}), 1500 (C=N_{str}), 1278 (C=C_{str}), 960–812 (C-H_{def}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) : δ_H 1.09 (3H, t, J_{HH} 4.76 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.47 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.04 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 7.01–7.66 (7H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 171.88, 165.92, 162.99, 151.33, 137.57, 133.73, 132.41, 128.14, 126.08, 125.57, 124.52, 122.97, 122.07, 121.69, 117.66, 116.07, 59.26, 23.11, 14.04; ESI-MS : m/z Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆N₂Cl₂O₂S : 419.41, Found : [M]⁺ 419.6; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 57.22; H, 3.81; N, 6.77. Found : C, 57.19; H, 3.84; N, 6.76.

9-Phenyl-6,6-dimethyl-5,6,7,9-tetrahydro-4H-1,2,4-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-8-one (2a) :

White powder, m.p. 230–232 °C, $R_f = 0.58$ (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 2850 (C-H_{str}), 1645 (C=O_{str}), 1587 (C-H_{def}), 1483 (C-H_{def}), 1454 (N-H_{str}), 1270 (C-N_{str}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 0.96 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.05 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.17 (1H, d, J_{HH} 6.52 Hz, H-5), 2.19 (1H, d, J_{HH} 12.52 Hz, H-5'), 2.23–2.59 (2H, m, H-7), 6.44 (1H, s, H-9), 7.07–7.48 (5H,

m, ArH), 7.66 (1H, s, H-2), 8.1 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 149.39, 147.82, 146.63, 129.43, 128.24, 127.34, 126.08, 122.77, 120.72, 119.81, 115.78, 110.66, 109.02, 55.47, 13.91; ESI-MS : *m/z* Calcd. for : C₁₇H₁₈N₄O : 294.34, Found : [M+H]⁺ 295; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 69.30; H, 6.11; N, 19.02. Found : C, 69.46; H, 6.19; N, 19.09.

9-(2-Hydroxy phenyl)-6,6-dimethyl-5,6,7,9-tetrahydro-4H-1,2,4-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-8-one (2b) :

White powder, m.p. 112–114 °C, *R_f* = 0.56 (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (*ν*_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 2850 (C-H_{str}), 1625 (C=O_{str}), 1585 (C-H_{def}), 1510 (C-H_{def}), 1427 (N-H_{str}), 1269 (C-N_{str}), 864–1124 (C-H_{def}); NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 0.98, (3H, s, CH₃), 1.02, (3H, s, CH₃), 2.33 (1H, d, *J*_{HH} 3.36 Hz, H-5), 2.4 (1H, d, *J*_{HH} 1.80 Hz, H-5'), 2.57–2.78 (2H, m, H-7), 6.49 (1H, s, H-9), 6.85–7.36 (5H, m, ArH), 7.62 (1H, s, H-2), 8.29 (1H, s, NH), 9.18 (1H, s, OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 153.95, 152.63, 151.46, 132.18, 130.90, 127.71, 125.91, 124.45, 121.73, 121.53, 120.57, 111.53, 110.74, 13.60; ESI-MS : *m/z* Calcd. for : C₁₇H₁₈N₄O₂ : 310.3, Found : [M-H]⁺ 309; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 65.74; H, 5.80; N, 18.04. Found : C, 65.89; H, 5.76; N, 18.16.

4-(2-Hydroxy phenyl)-7,7-dimethyl-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazoline-2,5-dione (3a) :

White powder, m.p. 140–142 °C, *R_f* = 0.57 (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (*ν*_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 3404 (OH_{str}), 2850 (C-H_{str}), 1615 (C=O_{str}), 1575 (C-H_{def}), 1510 (C-H_{def}), 1427 (N-H_{str}), 1269 (C-N_{str}), 864 (C-H_{def}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 0.99 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.07 (1H, s, CH₃), 2.14 (1H, s, CH₂), 2.4 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.54 (1H, s, CH), 7.08–7.48 (4H, m, ArH), 8.1 (2H, broad band, NH), 11.91 (1H, s, OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 162.99, 147.65, 145.57, 141.42, 140.27, 129.60, 126.96, 126.17, 115.73, 115.44, 55.44, 30.48, 29.49, 27.79; ESI-MS : *m/z* Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₈N₂O₃ : 286.36. Found : [M-H]⁺ 285.3; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 67.04; H, 6.28; N, 9.77. Found : C, 67.16; H, 6.22; N, 9.91.

4-Phenyl-7,7-dimethyl-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazoline-2-thione (3b) :

White powder, m.p. 162–164 °C, *R_f* = 0.56 (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (*ν*_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 2650 (C-H_{str}), 1645 (C=O_{str}), 1587 (C-H_{def}), 1554 (C-H_{def}), 1483 (N-

H_{str}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 0.98 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.10 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.22 (1H, s, CH₂), 2.46 (1H, s, CH₂), 4.74 (1H, s, CH), 7.08–7.48 (5H, m, ArH), 8.08 (2H, broad band, NH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 162.39, 140.39, 129.43, 128.24, 127.34, 126.08, 122.77, 120.72, 119.81, 115.58, 55.47, 30.42, 29.29, 27.44; ESI-MS : *m/z* Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₈N₂OS : 286.38, Found : [M-H]⁺ 285.3; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 67.04; H, 6.28; N, 9.77. Found : C, 67.21; H, 6.33; N, 9.89.

12-Phenyl-substituted-2,3,4,12-tetrahydrobenzo[4,5]thiazolo[2,3-b]quinazolin-1-one (4) :

Pale yellow powder, m.p. 230–232 °C, *R_f* = 0.53 (DCM : toluene; 3 : 2); IR (KBr) (*ν*_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 3007 (C-H_{str}), 2922 (C-H_{str}), 1625 (C=O_{str}), 1510 (C-H_{def}), 1267 (N-H_{str}), 1122 (C=S_{str}), 962–812 (C-H_{str}); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ_H 0.93 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.09 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.18–2.30 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.52 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.53 (1H, s, CH), 7.17–7.53 (9H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) : 191.12, 182.89, 149.12, 147.75, 140.37, 130.34, 129.81, 126.21, 123.90, 123.46, 122.72, 120.79, 115.77, 115.52, 110.66, 100.78, 55.47; ESI-MS : *m/z* Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₀N₂OS : 360.42, Found : [M+H]⁺ 361.3; C, H and N analyses Calcd. for : C, 73.24; H, 5.54; N, 7.76. Found : C, 73.29; H, 5.65; N, 7.83.

3. Pharmacology

3.1. Radical-scavenging activity and antioxidant activity of nitrogen heterocycles :

Radical-scavenging activity of synthesized nitrogen heterocyclic derivatives belonging different structural classes was analyzed by the DPPH•³³, superoxide radical³⁴ and nitric oxide radical scavenging methods³⁵ to evaluated the radical scavenging activity followed by the screening of their reducing ability (Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power), metal chelating activity and total antioxidant activity.

3.2. To determine MIC by the micro dilution broth susceptibility test :

Different concentrations 20, 10, 5, 2.5, 1.25 and 0.625 µg/ml of the compound (**1a-h**, **2a**, **2b**, **3a**, **3b** and **4**) was prepared in sterile microwell to determine minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). Nutrient broth was adjusted to pH 7.0 used for the determination of MIC. The inoculums of the test microorganisms were prepared by

using 16 hold cultures adjusted by reference to the 0.5 McFarland standards (1.5×10^8 CFU/mL). Brain heart infusion broth was prepared and 150 μ L of it was taken in each well and 10 μ L of each compound was added in broth with different concentrations, then 10 μ L of bacterial culture broth was added. The plate was shaken to uniformly mix the inoculums with the broth. Optical density was taken by photo spectrometer (μ Quant, Biotek Ltd., USA) and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. Appearance of any turbidity shows that the compound is not able to inhibit the growth of the bacteria, while no turbidity indicates the inhibition of microorganism by the sample (Table 1).

Subourad dextrose agar was prepared and 150 μ L of it was taken in each well and 10 μ L of each compound was added in broth with different concentrations, then 10 μ L of fungi culture broth was added. The plate was shaken to uniformly mix the inoculums with the broth and note the optical density. The well incubated for 72 h at 28 °C. Appearance of any turbidity shows that the compound is not able to inhibit the growth of the bacteria, while no turbidity indicates the inhibition of microorganism by the sample. To ensure that solvent had no effect on fungal growth a control test was performed with test medium supplemented with acetone at the same dilutions as used in the experiment. The results incorporated in Table 1.

Table 1. The *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activity (MIC₉₅ in μ g/ml) of the synthesized compounds

Comps.	Bacteria strains			Fungal strains		
	<i>B. subtilis</i> (ATCC 530)	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (ATCC 16425)	<i>E. faecalis</i> (ATCC 29212)	<i>C. neoformans</i> (ATCC 10231)	<i>C. albicans</i> (ATCC 22019)	<i>Rhizopus</i> sp. (ATCC 2842)
1a	5	–	5	–	10	2.5
1b	5	–	5	5	–	–
1c	2.5	5	2.5	1.25	1.25	–
1d	0.625	1.25	2.5	1.25	0.625	2.5
1e	–	10	5	–	2.5	1.25
1f	1.25	–	1.25	5	2.5	–
1g	–	1.25	0.625	2.5	1.25	–
1h	–	–	20	–	–	2.5
2a	–	–	5	2.5	–	2.5
2b	1.25	2.5	2.5	1.25	0.625	1.25
3a	5	2.5	1.25	–	–	–
3b	1.25	5	1.25	2.5	1.25	1.25
4	2.5	5	2.5	–	0.625	2.5
Acetone	–	–	–	–	–	–
Ciprofloxacin ^b	1.25	2.5	1.25	0.625	1.25	1.25
Fluconazole ^c						
Inoculum control	Growth in all concentration	Growth in all concentration	Growth in all concentration	Growth in all concentration	Growth in all concentration	Growth in all concentration
Broth control	No growth	No growth	No growth	No growth	No growth	No growth

(–) Resistant

^aMIC (μ M) = Minimum inhibitory concentration . ^bStandard drug for antibacterial study. ^cStandard drug for antifungal study.

3.3. *In vitro*-antifungal test³⁶ :

For antifungal testing the heterocyclic derivatives and fluconazole (standard drug) solution was prepared in acetone at initial concentration (120 μ g/mL) and serially diluted to make effective concentration of 20, 10, 5.0, 2.5, 1.25, 0.625 and 0.315 μ g/mL. Isolated fungal species *A. niger*, *A. fumigates* and *A. flavus* were selected.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Chemistry :

In order to evaluate the reaction conditions, a model reaction of benzaldehyde (0.0025 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.0025 mol) and 2-amino benzothiazole (0.0025 mol) was carried out using different catalyst, temperature and mol% under solvent free conditions. Lower yield and

higher reaction time was requiring when reaction carried out at room temperature. As reaction temperature was increases, reaction has completed with lower time with slightly improvement in yield but it was not increased more with increasing the reaction temperature (90 °C). So, 70 °C temperature was found optimum temperature for further study. In term of catalyst was used, the best results were obtained with catalyst loading of 10 mol% for L-proline. It was found to be the optimal quantity (Table 2, Entry 5). Other metal catalysts have given moderate yield (41–49%). Only acetic acid has given 67% yield which was rather better than other metal catalyst

Table 2. Optimization of reaction conditions^a

Entry	Catalyst (mol %/mg)	Temp. (°C)	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^b
1	No catalyst	30	48	10
2	No catalyst	70	20	25
3	No catalyst	90	20	26
4	L-Proline (5)	70	8	64
5	L-Proline (10)	70	4	88
6	L-Proline (15)	70	4	88
7	L-Proline (20)	70	4	88
8	Acetic acid (10)	70	18	67
9	SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (10)	70	12	45
10	LiCl (10)	70	15	41
11	AlCl ₃ (10)	70	15	49
12	SrCl ₂ .6H ₂ O (10)	70	10	43
13	Mg(NO ₃) ₂ (10)	70	12	47

^aThree component reaction of benzaldehyde (0.0025 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.0025 mol) and 2-amino benzothiazole (0.0025 mol) carried out. ^bIsolated yield.

but not than L-prolin. Thus, considering the overall effects of reaction time, temperature and catalyst loading, ensuing studies on the exploration of substrate scope were performed at 65–70 °C.

The methodology involves one-pot, three component reaction of aldehydes (0.0025 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.0025 mol) and 2-amino benzothiazole (0.0025 mol) using L-proline as a catalyst under solvent free conditions at 65–70 °C (Table 3, Scheme 1). The structure of pyrimidine derivatives has been confirmed on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, Mass spectral and elemental analysis.

Reaction conditions in hand, 1,2,4-triazoloquinazoline derivatives **2** were synthesized using aldehydes, dimedone and 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole at 65–70 °C under solvent free

conditions. To further expand the scope of present method, we have investigated the one-pot reactions involving urea/thiourea/2-amino benzothiazole and dimedone with aldehydes (Scheme 2). Under the above optimized conditions, the reactions proceed smoothly and a variety of desired products viz. 1,2,4-triazoloquinazoline **2**, octahydroquinazolinone **3** and fused thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolinone **4** derivatives were obtained in good yields (Table 4). A variety of electron donating and electron withdrawing groups on different substituted aromatic aldehydes have been studied. There is no significant effect of substituents on phenyl ring. The reaction using 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole was faster than that observed using urea, thiourea and 2-amino benzothiazole. Synthesis using urea and thiourea gave better yield and was faster than that observed using 2-amino benzothiazole (Table 4). It may be due to steric hindrance of benzothiazole moiety, as sterically hindered substrates proceeded slowly.

4.2. Radical-scavenging and antioxidant activities of nitrogen heterocycles :

Free radical scavenging is one of the best known mechanisms by which antioxidant inhibit lipid peroxidation. Antioxidant studies viz. DPPH, superoxide and nitric oxide radical scavenging activity evaluation are standard assays and offer rapid techniques for screening the radical scavenging activity (RSA) of specific compounds. Antioxidant activity for all the compounds was done using DPPH in methanolic solution. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard. A stock solution (200, 100, 50, 25, 12.5 µg/ml) of 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole, fused thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolinone, octahydroquinazolinone and 1,2,4-triazoloquinazoline derivatives was prepared by serial dilution method. The results are showed in the Fig. 1. The present study showed that among 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole derivatives, hydroxyl derivatives (**1b**, **1e** and **1f**) exhibited excellent antioxidant activity. It may be due to presence of additional hydroxyl groups in molecules, because literature shows that hydroxyl groups are responsible for antioxidant activity³⁷. Introduction of dimethylamino and nitro groups at *para* position showed significant antioxidant activity. Molecules possess core structure as quinazolinone and quinazoline (derivatives **2a**, **2b**, **3a** and **3b**) showed the broad spectrum of antioxidant activity. Surprisingly, fused thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolinone **4** also possessed significant activity.

Table 3. Synthesis of 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole (**1a-h**) derivatives

Entry	Aldehydes	Product	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^a	M.p. (°C)
1	 1a	120	88	178–180	
2	 1b	120	84	192–194	
3	 1c	110	82	175–178	
4	 1d	120	86	170–172	
5	 1e	100	81	212–215	
6	 1f	110	86	210–212	
7	 1g	120	79	130–132	
8	 1h	110	85	150–152	

^aIsolated yield.

Scheme 1. Preparation of 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole derivatives.

Scheme 2. L-Proline catalyzed synthesis of octahydroquinazolines, 1,2,4-triazoloquinazolines and fused thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolinone.

Table 4. L-Proline catalyzed synthesis of nitrogen heterocycles^a

Aldehydes	Product	Triazole/urea/thiourea	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^a	M.p. (°C)
			15	94	230–232
		2a			
			15	91	112–114
		2b			
			18	82	140–142
		3a			

	25	96	162–164		
		3b			
	60	89	230–232		
		4			

^aReaction conditions : dimedone (0.0025 mol), aldehydes (0.0025 mol), urea/thiourea/3-amino-1,2,4-triazole/2-amino benzothiazole (0.0025 mol), L-proline (10 mol%), heating at 65–70 °C. ^bIsolated yield.

Fig. 1. Results of antioxidant activity by DPHH• method.

In superoxide radical scavenging assay 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole derivatives **1b** and **1e** showed the excellent activity. Derivatives **1b** and **1f** have electron donating substituent on *para* position, in spite of that **1b** showed slightly higher scavenging activity. It showed the involvement of another electron donating substituent at *meta* position (methoxy group). From Fig. 2, it is clear that derivative **2b** and **3a** showed the higher activity due to quinazolinone moieties have hydroxyl substituent at *ortho* position. Thus the superoxide scavenging property decreases as **1b** > **2b** > **3a** > **1e** > **1f**. The re-

sults from above experiments thus confirm that hydroxyl substituent at both position (*ortho* and *para*) more pronounced effect in 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole and quinoline ring system.

The nitric oxide scavenging capacity helps to arrest the chain of reactions initiated by excess generation of NO• that are detrimental to human health. Nitric oxide is also implicated for inflammation, cancer and other pathological conditions. It is clear from the Fig. 3, derivatives **1a**, **1c**, **1g** and **2a** showed the lower scavenging effect as against **1b** (76%), **1f** (79%), **2b** (78%) and **3a** (74%) of

Fig. 2. Antioxidant activity by superoxide radical method.

Fig. 3. Antioxidant activity by nitric oxide radical method.

NO, respectively. In this assay compound **2b** showed the highest activity which might be due to quinoline moiety have hydroxyl substituent. Overall nitric oxide scavenging capacity decreases in the order **2b** > **1f** > **1b** > **3a**. Thus we have shown that the quinoline moiety (**2b**) possessed considerable nitric oxide scavenging antioxidant capacity and its efficiency as an anti oxidative agent will be confirm using various assay in future.

4.3. Antibacterial activity :

Susceptibility test *in vitro* was done on bacteria *Bacillus cereus* (MTCC 7350), *Enterococcus faecalis* (ATCC 16425) and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 29212). Each

test was performed in triplicate and the MICs reported represent the best of at least two repetitions. Ciprofloxacin is used as standard antibacterial drug.

Structure activity relationship :

An investigation of the *in vitro* antibacterial activity profile of synthesized heterocycles gives a clear picture of structure activity relationship. From the data in Table 1, derivatives **1c** (4-dimethylamino) and **1d** (4-nitro) showed the excellent antibacterial activity against all tested bacterial strains. Electron withdrawing group (derivatives **1d**) demonstrated better activity to ciprofloxacin against *B. subtilis* and *K. pneumoniae* with 0.625 µg/ml and 1.25

µg/ml respectively. SAR data also revealed that electron releasing group as hydroxyl (**1f**) and methoxy (**1g**) showed the significant activity. Derivative **1f** showed the equipotent antibacterial activity to ciprofloxacin against *B. subtilis* and *E. faecalis* with 1.25 µg/ml. *Ortho* and *meta* substitution (derivatives **1b**, **1e** and **1g**) retarded the efficiency of antibacterial activity. Molecules possess the 1,2,4-triazoloquinazoline (**2a** and **2b**), octahydroquinazolinone (**3a** and **3b**) and fused thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolinone (**4**) moieties as core structure exhibited a broad spectrum of antibacterial activity. Overall structure activity relationship showed the *para* substituted derivatives possess excellent antibacterial activity.

4.4. Antifungal activity :

We have evaluated *in vitro* antifungal activity against *Cryptococcus neoformans* (ATCC 10231), *Candida albicans* (ATCC 22019) and *Rhizopus* sp. (ATCC 2842). Fluconazole used as standard drug.

Structure activity relationship :

From the results shown in Fig. 4 and Table 1, concluded a qualitative structure activity relationship. Electron withdrawing group (compound **1d**) showed the excellent antifungal activity against all tested fungal strains

dimethylamino group at *para* position retarded the efficiency against *Rhizopus* sp. and showed the good activity against *C. neoformans* and *C. albicans* with MIC of 1.25 µg/ml which is equipotent to ciprofloxacin. Further SAR suggests that hydroxyl group at *ortho* position (**2e**) don't show significant efficiency but *para* substituted derivative (**2f**) showed significant MIC values against *C. neoformans* and *C. albicans*. Regarding SAR of fused thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolinone, octahydroquinazolinone and 1,2,4-triazoloquinazoline derivatives, derivative **2b**, **3b** and **4** showed excellent antifungal spectrum against all tested fungal strains. Octahydroquinazolinone derivative **3a** didn't show antifungal activity. Overall study showed that little structure modification can immense biological effect.

4.5. Cytotoxicity against LI23 (Human lung cells) :

Cytotoxicity was performed by MTT assay method^{38,39}. A 96-well flat bottom tissue culture plate was seeded with 2×10^3 cells in 0.1 ml of MEM medium supplemented with 10% FBS and allowed to attach for 24 h. After 24 h of incubation, cells were treated with test compounds to get a concentration of 5, 10, 20, 50 100 and 200 µM/ml incubated for 48 h. The cells in the

Fig 4. Comparable chart for MIC₉₅ of heterocycles against tested bacterial and fungal strain.

among other 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole derivatives. Derivatives **1d** showed the better activity to fluconazole against *C. albicans* with 0.625 µg/ml. Introduction of

control group received only the medium containing the 0.2% DMSO. Each treatment was performed in duplication. After the treatment, drug containing media was re-

moved and washed with 200 μL of PBS. To each well of the 96 well plate, 100 μL of MTT reagent (Stock : 1 mg/ml in serum free medium) was added and incubated for 4 h at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. After 4 h of incubation the plate was inverted on tissue paper to remove the MTT reagent. To solubilize formazan crystals in the wells, 100 μL of 100% DMSO was added to each well. The optical density was mea-

sured by microtiter plate reader at 590 nm. Compound concentration (μM) required to reduce the viability of mock-infected cells by 50% as determined by MTT method which summarized in Fig. 5. Results of MTT assay mentioned on the cell viability based on ability to metabolize the compounds.

Results of MTT assay mentioned on the cell viability

Fig. 5. Cytotoxicity of synthesized compounds against L123 human lung cells.

Scheme 3. Plausible reaction mechanism using L-proline.

based on ability to metabolize the compounds. The results observed in the cytotoxicity assay in L123 human lung cells (Fig. 3) showed that the 4*H*-pyrimido[2,1-*b*][1,3]benzothiazole derivatives showed good activity except **1b** (4-hydroxy-3-methoxy) and **1f** (4-hydroxy) with 50 µM/mL. In case of 1,2,4-triazoloquinazolines, octahydroquinazolinones and fused thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolinon, derivatives **2a** and **3a** demonstrated toxic effect on cell line.

4.6. Plausible reaction mechanism :

A proposed mechanism for one-pot reaction using aldehydes, dicarbonyl and amine scaffold is shown in Scheme 3.

There is evidence in the literature that L-proline can catalyze aldol related reactions such as Knoevenagel condensation as well as Michael addition⁴⁰⁻⁴². In this reaction, we suggest that L-proline is an effective catalyst for formation of iminium ion **5** in a reversible reaction with benzaldehyde. The higher reactivity of iminium ion facilitates the Knoevenagel condensation for formation of intermediate **6**. Then intermediate **6** is reacted with amine scaffold through Michael addition to form the target product.

5. Conclusion

It can be concluded that we have synthesized the library of heterocyclic compounds using one-pot three component reaction of substituted aromatic aldehydes, 1,3-dicarbonyl and urea/thiourea/2-amino benzothiazole/3-amino-1,2,4-triazole in the presence of L-proline as catalyst under solvent free conditions. The operational simplicity and availability of starting material makes it a rather forward alternative procedure than traditional multi-step methods. Synthesized compounds were screened for their antioxidant and antimicrobial activity. The compounds **1b**, **2b**, **3a**, **1e** and **1f** have shown promising antioxidant activity whereas compounds **1b**, **1e**, **1g**, **2a**, **2b**, **3a**, **3b** and **4** have exhibited excellent antimicrobial activity. The main advantages of this methodology are the short reaction times, simple catalyst system, higher yields, free of organic solvents and ease of work-up procedure.

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